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An Approach to the Performance of Passport Services through Workload and Work Environment: Study at the Wonosobo Immigration Office

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the effect of workload and work environment on the performance of passport issuance services at the Wonosobo Immigration Office. Workload is defined as a series of tasks that must be carried out by a work unit within an organization or by an individual who serves in a position within a certain period of time. Meanwhile, the work environment is defined as a place where a worker completes his duties in accordance with the goals to be achieved. There is a mismatch in the number of human resources in passport services compared to the high level of passport applications. The research method used in this research is quantitative method. Data collection was carried out through observation and distribution of questionnaires. Sampling using total sampling techniques, and data analysis was carried out using a Likert scale. The data analysis technique applied in this study is using multiple linear regression data analysis techniques. The results of data collection show the significance of workload of 0.32 and work environment of 0.21 greater than 0.05, which means that there is an influence of workload and work environment on employee performance in passport services. This study recommends increasing the number of human resources and improving the work environment to improve the performance of passport issuance services.

Keywords: Workload, Work Environment, Performance of Passport Issuance Services

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Humans are always involved in social life and organizations in various aspects of their lives. This is very evident in their daily life in the home environment, in social groups, educational institutions, and in various other aspects of life, because it is needed to meet the needs of his life (Bründl et al., 2017).

According to an article by Costanza (2007), efforts to meet the needs of human life need to work, because by working humans can meet all their needs. One form of human community is the population. A population is a group of humans who live in a certain area. Population growth in Indonesia is currently very high which causes difficult employment. This makes many Indonesian citizens flock to complain their fate in other countries.

With many cases of Indonesian citizens who go to many other countries to become Indonesian migrant employees, it has led to an increase in international crossings. The increasing opening of international crossings has led to increasing demands for immigration services. The implementation of services in the field of immigration carried out by human resources includes Indonesian immigration personnel. Immigration services that are required to be good must be jointly followed by an increase in human resources (Low, 2021).

1.2 Explore Importance of the Problem

According to the provisions of the Minister of Law and Human Rights' Regulation Number 23 of 2019 regarding the Organisation and Work Procedures of the Immigration Office, Wonosobo Immigration Office is one of the technical task implementation units in the field of immigration in the Central Java region. One of the duties and functions of the Wonosobo Immigration Office is to provide immigration services, which include immigration stay permit services and passport making services. Passport services at the Wonosobo Immigration Office are divided into 2 (two) places, namely at the Wonosobo Immigration Office and the Magelang Immigration Office Work Unit.

Based on data obtained from the Immigration Office, in 2022 there were 35,854 passport applications. If calculated every month there are 2,988 passport issuances and every day there are approximately 100 passport issuances. Based on the passport statistics report of the Wonosobo Immigration Office, passport applications every day are not comparable to the number of employees in the passport service subsection which only amounts to nine employees. Based on these data, it can be seen that until now there is still no effort from the government to overcome the problem of the gap between the implementation of duties and functions with the number of existing employees. If left unchecked, it can result in a decrease in employee performance, especially in employee motivation and productivity.

Increasing the efficiency of immigration service performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office can be achieved if it is supported by a conducive work environment and atmosphere, including the provision of adequate and well-organized space. A good working environment is very important for the smooth running of the duties of Wonosobo Immigration Office employees, so it is also necessary to prepare a comfortable working environment and conducive office atmosphere, as well as proper room arrangement.

A pleasant, comfortable work environment and a conducive office atmosphere will create comfort for employees, it allows employees to work optimally and has a direct effect on carrying out their duties with full responsibility. Inadequate work environment conditions can cause high levels of stress in employees, increase the risk of illness, and hinder employees' ability to concentrate which can reduce productivity at work (Rasool et al., 2021).

A good working atmosphere is created by a well-organized organization, but if the organization is not well-organized, it will lead to an unclear division of labor and confusing channels of assignment and responsibility that can affect employee performance to work optimally. Workload levels, work environment conditions, and performance have a significant impact on the operational sustainability of an office (Irawanto et al., 2021).

1.3 Describe Relevant Scholarship

1.3.1 Workload

Workload refers to a series of tasks that must be carried out by a work unit in an organization or by an individual who serves in a position, within a predetermined period of time. According to Hancock et al. (2019) workload

reflects the number of tasks assigned to an employee. Excessive workload is one of the triggers for work stress which can lead to a decrease in the quality of work performed.

According to Matthew et al (2020) workload is the difference between a worker's ability and capacity in carrying out the required tasks. Moreover, the fact that humans have properties related to physical and mental, therefore each person has a different level of burden.

According to Kramer (2020), workload is a condition where there are demands from work that must be completed within a predetermined time. Workload can also mean that in each of the tasks completed there are differences in the level of employee ability and employee capacity in completing the work they face with a certain period of time.

According to Staats et al. (2020), workload is the method through which an individual carries out his or her job tasks or a group of jobs that must be completed under regular circumstances at a specific period. Drawing from multiple prior interpretations, it may be inferred that the concept of workload refers to the instances in which an individual is faced with superfluous expectations that surpass their typical capacity and aptitude to work. Employee productivity may suffer if they are given excessive work to do, which will ultimately affect the organization's success.

1.3.2 Work Environment

According to Toropova et al. (2021), one of the factors that inspires workers to provide their best effort is a perfect work environment. López-Cabarcos et al. (2022) define a work environment as a location where individuals carry out tasks linked to their jobs. Due to its potential to impact the calibre of work output, the workplace environment is particularly relevant.

Hansel et al (2024) define the work environment as something that can influence employees to carry out the tasks ordered to them, which in turn can affect discipline at work. So, the definition of work environment is a place where a worker completes his tasks in accordance with the goals to be achieved. Hansel also said that work environment has an influence on work results.

When the workplace environment is safe and comfortable, it will enable work to be done easily and subsequently get better work results. If the work environment does not provide a sense of comfort for workers, it will cause boredom and feelings of discomfort which will ultimately have an undesirable impact on the organisation. Therefore, the work environment should be used as a way to maximise worker performance and make them comfortable in completing their work (Putri et al., 2019).

1.4 Problem Formulations

The following is the formulation of the hypothesis of this study using a 95% confidence level, $\alpha = 0.05$:

H1: Workload affects Passport Service Performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office

H2: Work Environment affects the Performance of Passport Services at the Wonosobo Immigration Office

H3: Workload and Work Environment simultaneously affect the Performance of Passport Services at the Wonosobo Immigration Office.

2. Method

This research uses quantitative methods, namely with survey techniques and using questionnaires as instruments for the sample. The use of questionnaires is to collect information which is then used as a tool to assess associations and individual behavior (Sugiyono, 2017).

Surveys are one of the tools used in quantitative research methodologies to gather data from a sample of people, or respondents. In this study, written questionnaires were employed to gather primary data. After the survey, the

data collected are statistically evaluated to produce insightful study findings. Surveys can help researchers communicate new features or trends to their respondents and gather enough data to gain information fast and efficiently (Sugiyono, 2017).

2.1 Participant (Subject) Characteristics

In this study, the population was employees at the Wonosobo Immigration Office. Wonosobo Immigration Office was chosen because it has a fairly high workload in passport issuance services, especially in Central Java Province. To facilitate service, recently Wonosobo Immigration Office also has a representative office in Magelang City. Currently, the number of employees at the Wonosobo Immigration Office is 42 people, as shown in the following table:

Table 1: Characteristics by Gender

Gender	Total	Percentage (%)
Men	33	79 %
Women	9	21%
Total	42	100 %

Source: Primary data processed 2024

Characteristics of respondents of Wonosobo Immigration Office employees based on age are presented in the following table:

Table 2: Characteristics by Age

Age	Total	Percentage (%)
<25 years old	3	7%
26-35 years old	12	29%
36-45 years old	20	48%
>46 years old	7	17%
Total	42	100%

Source: Primary data processed 2024

2.2 Sampling Procedures

Samples in quantitative research are subsets of the population that contain several individuals with comparable features. The Saturated Sampling Technique, according to Sugiyono (2017), is a sample selection technique in which every member of the population is selected as a sample. Since the Wonosobo Immigration Office employed the Total Sampling Technique as the sampling method for this study, every employee was included in the sample. The following is a table of the results of distributing questionnaires.

Table 3: Questionnaire Distribution

Description	Jumlah
Questionnaires that have been distributed	42
Successfully collected questionnaires	42
Questionnaires can be processed	42
Questionnaires can not be processed	0

Source: Primary data processed 2024

The results of the data collection through the distribution of questionnaires showed positive achievements, especially as all the questionnaires were successfully collected in accordance with the sample predetermined in the research planning stage.

3. Results

3.1 Classical Assumption Test

3.1.1 Normality Test

The normality test in this study was carried out using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. The results provide a significance value that will help in assessing the normality of the data. If the significance value resulting from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test is greater than 0.05, this indicates that the residuals in this regression model fulfil the assumption of normality. In other words, the distribution of residuals can be considered close to a normal distribution.

Table 4: Normality Test

One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		42
Normal Parameters a,b	Mean	.000000
	Std. Deviation	1.452965 20
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.129
	Positive	.109
	Negative	-.129
Test Statistic		.129
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.075 ^c
a. Test distribution is Normal.		

Source: Primary data processed 2024

From the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results listed in the table above, it can be concluded that the Significance value is 0.075. This figure exceeds the commonly used threshold of 0.05. With a significance value higher than 0.05, this indicates that the data used in this study has characteristics that approach or follow the normal distribution.

3.1.2 Multicollinearity test

To determine if the independent variables in a regression model have a strong link, multicollinearity testing is utilised. A decent regression model is typically distinguished by the lack of a significant correlation between the independent variables. A technique to identify potential multicollinearity is to calculate the variance inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance. When the VIF exceeds 10 or the tolerance value is less than 0.10, multicollinearity is indicated. (Ghozali, 2018).

Table 5: Multicollinearity Test

		Coefficients ^a				Collinearity Statistics	
Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients					
Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	7.672	2.543		3.017	.004	
	Workload	.245	.110	.329	2.230	.032	.776

Work	.360	.150	.353	2.396	.776	
Environment					.021	1.288

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Primary data processed 2024

The multicollinearity test results are displayed in the table above, where it is evident that the tolerance values for the workload (X1) and work environment (X2) variables are both 0.776. In addition, 1.288 is the VIF value for both the Workload variable (X1) and the Work Environment variable (X2).

The interpretation of these results is that the tolerance values for both independent variables, namely Workload (X1) and Work Environment (X2), are much greater than the 0.10 threshold often used as an indicator of multicollinearity. In addition, the VIF values for both are also well below the threshold of 10, confirming that there is no multicollinearity problem between all the independent variables in the regression model.

3.1.3 Heteroscedasticity test

The purpose of the heteroscedasticity test is to ascertain whether the residual variation in the regression model between data is non-uniform. The White test method was applied in this investigation.

Table 6: Heteroscedasticity Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	RSquare	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.451 ^a	.203	.092	3.12338
Predictors:	(Constant),	X1X2,	X2.	X1, X1 KUADRAT, X2 KUADRAT

Source: Primary data processed 2024

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the R Square value is 0.203. Then the data is calculated using the formula ($N * R \text{ Square}$) where N is the number of research respondents totalling 42 respondents. Then obtained c2 count ($42 \times 0.203 = 8.526$). And c2 table is calculated by looking at the df value, namely 5 with an alpha of 0.05, which is obtained 11.0705. From the data above, it is known that c2 count is smaller than c2 table, namely $8.526 < 11.0705$. It can be concluded that using the White test in this study there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

3.2 Statistics and Data Analysis

3.2.1 Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

The purpose of multiple linear regression testing is to determine whether the workload and work environment at the Wonosobo Immigration Office have an effect on the quality of passport services provided. Following data processing with the SPSS 24 programme, the following multiple linear regression test results were obtained:

Table 7: Multiple Linear Regression Test

Coefficients ^a					
Model		UnstandardizedB	Coeffici ents Std. Error	Standardi zed t Coefficients Beta	Sig.
1	(Constant)	7.672	2.543	3.017	.004
	Workload	.245	.110	.329	.032

Work Environment	.360	.150	.353	2.396	.021
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a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Primary data processed 2024

The Constant value (a) in the table above is 7.672, while the X1 and X2 values (b / regression coefficients) are 0.245 and 0.360. These values allow the regression equation to be stated as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1.X_1 + b_2.X_2 \text{ atau } Y = 7,672 + 0,245 + 0,360$$

Meaning:

A constant of 7.672 indicates that the performance variable's consistent value is 7.672.

The X1 coefficient of regression of 0.245 means that the workload value will rise by 0.245 for every 1% increase in the workload value. This indicates that the workload value determined in this study will increase in proportion to the employee's actual workload.

Meanwhile, the 0.360 X2 regression coefficient shows that the Work Environment value will rise by 0.360 for every 1% increase in the Work Environment value. In this case, the greater the work environment value that can be noted in the study, the better the working conditions offered to employees.

Considering that both regression coefficients are positive, it can be said that variables X1 (workload) and X2 (work environment) have a positive influence on Y (performance). That is, the Wonosobo Immigration Office's passport services operate better the more work is done there and the better the work environment is. In the context of public services, this research emphasises the significance of effective management in relation to attempts to enhance the workload and work environment in order to achieve optimal performance levels.

Decision making in multiple regression tests:

- R Square of 0.342 indicates that workload and work environment have a 34.2% impact on performance, the dependent variable.
- The calculated F value of 10,158 > F Table with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05 shows that the elements of workload and work environment (X) have an impact on performance (Y). This implies that the regression model can be used to predict performance variables.

3.2.2 Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

The T test has the aim of measuring whether or not there is an independent (partial) influence shown by the workload and work environment variables (X) on the performance variable (Y). The basis for decision making in the T test is:

- It can be stated that there has been sufficient evidence to support the hypothesis that variable X influences variable Y if the calculated t value is higher than the matching table t value
- In contrast, there is not sufficient data to support the hypothesis that variable X influences variable Y if the calculated value of t is less than the matching t table value.

$$\text{Calculation of t table} = t(\alpha/2; n-k-1) = (0.05/2; 42-2-1) = t(0.023; 39) = 2.02269$$

Table 8: Multiple Linear Regression Test

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standard ized t Coefficients Beta	Sig.
1	(Constant)	7.672	2.543	3.017	.004

Workload	.245	.110	.329	2.230	.032
Work Environment	.360	.150	.353	2.396	.021

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Primary data processed 2024

- Testing the First Hypothesis (H1):
Since the calculated t value of 2.230 is higher than the t table of 2.02269, it may be said that H1 is accepted, indicating that X1 (workload) has a beneficial impact on Y (performance).
- Second Hypothesis Testing (H2):
Since the calculated t value of 2.396 is higher than the t table of 2.02269, it may be said that H2 is accepted, indicating that X2 (Work Environment) has a beneficial impact on Y (Performance).

3.2.3 F Test Results

To ascertain if the workload and work environment variables (X) have a substantial combined (simultaneous) effect on the performance variable (Y), the F test is used. The F test's decision-making framework is based on:

- There is sufficient data to conclude that variable X influences variable Y simultaneously if the significance value is less than 0.05 or the calculated F value is higher than the F table with a calculated F of 3.23..
- In contrast, there is insufficient evidence to conclude that variable X and variable Y are affected simultaneously if the significance value is higher than 0.05 or the calculated F value is lower than the F table with a calculated F of 3.23.

Table 9: F Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	45.087	2	22.5442	10.158	.000 ^b
	Residual	86.555	39	.219		
	total	131.643	41			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Environment, Workload

Source: Primary data processed 2024

According to the preceding table, the significant value for the simultaneous influence of X1 and X2 on Y is 0.000 <0.05, and the computed F value is 10.158 > F table 3.23. Thus, it can be said that H3 is acknowledged, showing that the Wonosobo Immigration Office's workload and work environment both affect passport service performance concurrently.

4. Discussion

4.1 The Effect of Workload on Passport Service Performance

According to the study's first hypothesis (H1), workload affects how well passport services are performed at the Wonosobo Immigration Office. The estimated t value, 2.230, is more than the t table value of 2.02269, according to data analysis. Thus, it can be said that H1 is accepted, suggesting that the Workload variable (X1) has a positive impact on the Performance variable (Y). The study's findings support the notion that performance in passport issuing services at the Wonosobo Immigration Office is significantly influenced by workload.

This research identifies that Workload is evaluated using five important indicators, namely achievement targets, job conditions, job standards, task authority, and responsibility. The results showed that the higher the workload experienced by employees without an appropriate division of tasks, the greater the negative impact on employee performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office. This can result in a decrease in employee productivity and work efficiency.

This finding is in line with the results of research conducted by Jahari (2019), Parulian et al. (2020), Rusmiati et al. (2021) which also showed that workload has a positive and significant effect on employee performance in several companies in Indonesia. Thus, it can be asserted that the role of Workload in influencing employee performance is a consistent phenomenon in the context of various immigration offices. This is because Indonesian society has a character that is not much different, especially in communities on the island of Java (Dewantara et al., 2019).

From the description above, it can be concluded that Workload does have a significant influence on Passport Service Performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office. These findings can provide a basis for decision making and management at the Immigration Office to design more effective strategies for managing workload and improving employee performance, with the aim of providing better passport services to the community in the future.

4.2 The Effect of Work Environment on Passport Service Performance

The study's second hypothesis (H2) asserts that the work environment at the Wonosobo Immigration Office affects the quality of passport services provided. The computed t value is 2.396, which is more than the t table value of 2.02269, according to the data analysis results. Therefore, it can be said that H2 is accepted, indicating that the Work Environment variable (X2) has a positive impact on the Performance variable (Y). This suggests that the performance of passport issuing services at the Wonosobo Immigration Office is significantly influenced by the work environment.

In this study, Work Environment is measured using 3 (three) important indicators, namely the work atmosphere, environmental conditions of the workplace, and the availability of equipment and facilities that can provide support for employee performance. A good layout in the workspace can increase employee morale and productivity. In addition, a positive working atmosphere and good co-operation between sections also play an important role in improving productivity and overall performance (López-Cabarcos et al., 2022).

This result is consistent with studies by Taheri et al. (2020) and Iis et al. (2022). Therefore, it can be said that, in the context of public service agencies, the influence of work environment on passport service performance is not just a local phenomenon but also broadly relevant.

From the description above, it can be concluded that the Work Environment does have a real influence on Passport Service Performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office, which can be the basis for related parties to make improvements and improvements to the Work Environment in order to improve the quality of public services in the future.

4.3 The Effect of Workload and Work Environment on Passport Service Performance

According to the third hypothesis (H3), the Wonosobo Immigration Office's passport service performance is concurrently impacted by workload and work environment. Based on data analysis, it is known that the calculated F value is $10.158 > F_{table} 3.23$ and the significance value for the simultaneous influence of X1 and X2 on Y is $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be concluded that H3 is accepted, meaning that work environment and workload have an impact on passport issuance services performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office simultaneously.. If the workload increases, it will cause employee performance to decrease because they cannot be maximised in carrying out their duties. The decline in employee performance, apart from being influenced by inappropriate

workload, is also influenced by work environment factors. Employees feel less enthusiastic if the spatial arrangement is poor. Coordination between sections is also needed to increase productivity at work. This is in line with research conducted by Tjiabrata et al. (2017), Asriani et al. (2018), and Musa & Suriadj (2020). Based on the description above, it is known that Workload and Work Environment when tested simultaneously have an influence on Passport Service Performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office.

5. Conclusion

Based on the discussion contained in the previous chapter, the results of research on the Effect of Workload and Work Environment on Passport Service Performance at the Wonosobo Immigration Office which consists of 3 (three) variables, namely workload variables (X1), work environment variables (X2), and performance variables (Y). The conclusions that can be drawn from the results of data processing are as follows:

- Workload (X1) has a significant influence on performance (Y) at the Immigration Office Class II Non TPI Wonosobo. The results of statistical analysis show that the higher the workload, the lower the performance of passport services.
- The work environment (X2) also has a significant effect on performance (Y). This indicates that good work environment conditions can improve passport service performance.
- The combination of workload (X1) and work environment (X2) variables together also has a significant effect on performance (Y). This indicates that both workload management and work environment improvements can help improve the performance of passport issuance services effectively and efficiently.

Thus, the results of this study underscore the importance of managing workload and creating a conducive work environment to improve passport service performance at the Wonosobo Class II Non TPI Immigration Office. Improvement efforts in this case can provide significant benefits for related parties in improving public services. Based on the results of the study, there is a fairly high workload of employees in the passport service section and a less supportive work environment. This is due to the addition of administrative work areas, namely the existence of the Immigration office work unit as a representative in Magelang, and Purworejo. To overcome the high workload and lack of work environment problems, it is recommended to the Wonosobo Immigration Office to propose additional employees with a high level of public service motivation. To overcome problems in the work environment, the following should be considered: 1) the office must create a comfortable community for its workers, 2) provision of adequate rest time, 3) provision of self-development opportunities, 4) provision of facilities and infrastructure that support the work environment (Britt, 2000).

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